

Briefing Memorandum on Golden Rice
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In August 2013 a small group of activists protesting the development of golden rice, a genetically modified organism (GMO), forcibly trespassed, maliciously trampled and partially destroyed an experimental growing plot for golden rice established by the Philippines government, the International Rice Research Institute, and other public sector partners. The claims made by protest organizers that a large group of Pilipino farmers (who were bussed to the protest site) were responsible for the damage, were later discredited¹.

Rice does not naturally contain vitamin A, a micronutrient vital for good human health. In Asia, where the poor rely on rice consumption for their daily diet, vitamin A deficiency (VAD) is a serious public health issue, killing or blinding an estimated 500,000 children and pregnant women annually. So the question is: how to get vitamin A to those who need it. One alternative being considered is to genetically modify rice so that it produces beta carotene, a pre-cursor substance that the human body uses to make vitamin A. Supporters argue golden rice is an effective means of delivering vitamin A to the poor who have traditionally relied on rice for their daily food survival. Those proponents such as the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), and the Department of Agriculture - Philippine Rice Research Institute argue GMO rice (called golden rice, because of its yellow color) is safe for humans and the environment (but they are conducting scientific testing and evaluations to confirm this position). The arguments against are wide ranging, from concern for long-term environmental health, to the nefarious. Greenpeace, for example, views golden rice as a threat to the environment; once introduced, never to be undone. Others, such as the Philippine-based organization Farmer Scientist Partnership for Development [MASIPAG] argue golden rice is simply a trick or deception, to achieve what ends is not clear. But according to the Future Tense blog cited above, the destruction of the golden rice experimental growing plot in 2013 was motivated by information that the the GMO rice project is central to a plot by foreign corporations to undermine Philippine sovereignty¹. Neither opponent offers evidence to support their concerns.

Planning the distribution of golden rice supporter's objectives are to maximize distribution of the GMO and thus to minimize the number of death and blindness cases from VAD. Ultimately the success of the distribution program would be measured by the criteria of percent reduction of the number of VAD deaths and injuries, with a target of 40 percent reduction by year five. Objective and criteria representative of the oppositions arguments are less clear and therefore lack distinction. However, for Greenpeace position these are appropriate: minimizing harm to the environment (objective) as measured by no collapse of other species resulting from the golden rice introduction. And perhaps for MASIPAG: minimizing foreign plots as measured by continued existence of the Philippine government. Regardless of the position on GMO, any alternative should have the attributes to protect human health and the environment.

There are other alternatives to address VAD among the poor. For example, dietary diversification, e.g., introduction of mangoes and sweet potatoes, and the use of vitamin supplements. The poor may not be able to afford such interventions, and the long term sustainability of program logistics are a concern. Another alternative is the use of black rice, a non-GMO seed developed by MASIPAG. A third alternative is to provide no cost medical care and diet/nutrition counseling to the poor. This alternative satisfy the attributes of protecting human health and the environment, but will be logistically and financially problematic. Nonetheless it should be considered and evaluated against the other alternatives.

As of May 2, 2016 according to the IRRI, golden rice continues to be evaluated. Meanwhile 500,000+ children and pregnant women die or go blind every year from VAD.

¹ Lynas, M., 2013. *The True Story About Who Destroyed a Genetically Modified Rice Crop*. [online Slate Magazine,] Available at: < http://www.slate.com/blogs/future_tense/2013/08/26/golden_rice_attack_in_philippines_anti_gmo_activists_lie_about_protest_and.html#return [Accessed: 2016, May 2]. Slate's Future Tense blog is a collaboration of Arizona State University and New America (non-partisan think tank).